

Data from satellite sensors: processing and application

Lecture: Recent research trends in ICT
Doctoral School of WUST

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Part I - Satellite data: acquisition and processing

>4500

SATELLITES
IN SPACE

>600

IMAGERY
SATELLITES

25 cm

BEST
RESOLUTION

- According to Euroconsult, in 2006-2015, 194 Earth observation satellites weighing more than 50 kg were put into orbits.
- In the period 2016-2025 it will be fired more than twice as many, i.e. 419 of those type of devices.

Commercial Satellite Imaging Market

PRESCIENT & STRATEGIC
INTELLIGENCE

Where knowledge inspires strategy

Market Growth
Will Accelerate
at a **CAGR**
(2022-2030)

11.2%

**MARKET
SIZE**

2022
USD 3,754 Mn

2030
USD 8,777 Mn

- Increasing investment in satellite technologies
- Advancements in sensing technologies

North America
Held Around
42% Share
in 2022

The commercial satellite imaging market size stood at USD 3.754 million in 2022, and it is expected to grow at a CAGR of 11.20% during 2022-2030, to reach USD 8.777 million by 2030.

Commercial Satellite Imaging Market By Application

Source: www.psmarketresearch.com

Satellite data applications

- the management of natural resources,
- protection of geographical borders,
- mapping of construction projects,
- in agricultural sector,
- monitoring the environment and climate change,
- mining and geology,
- construction and insurance services sectors,
- hazard monitoring,
- oceanography and fishing,
- vegetation and ecosystem dynamics,
- biodiversity conservation,
- cartography and landscape,
- forestry,
- regional planning, etc.

Polish companies have been participating in the European Space Agency projects for several years

The use of satellite data in Polish agriculture

Satellite image of a field sown with winter wheat, taken on March 27, 2016 and shared by SatAgro.

Detection of illegal construction based on satellite imagery (source: ProGea 4D sp. z .o.o.)

Urban Atlas

Satellite data is already used to support urban space management. For example, as part of the Urban Atlas project, land cover and land use maps were created for around 700 European agglomerations.

Based on images from the SPOT-5, ALOS, QuickBird and RapidEye satellites, a classification was made for all teams of urban centers inhabited by the population specified in the project. The developed maps have 20 classes according to the nomenclature used in CORINE Land Cover.

MONIT-AIR

In Poland, on the basis of WorldView-2 high resolution satellite imagery (DigitalGlobe, Maxar Technologies), object classification of land cover for Krakow and the surrounding area was made as part of the MONIT-AIR project "Integrated monitoring system for spatial data for improving air quality in Krakow" implemented by the City of Krakow, Faculty of Environmental Management and Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - National Research Institute, Cracow Branch.

The map of land cover classes was the result of object classification of WorldView-2 satellite imagery

Copernicus Hackathons

The Copernicus Hackathons are supported by organisers from 18 European countries in boosting the use of Earth observation (EO) data with a total of 40 events from 2018 to 2020. These Hackathons are opportunity for organisations to support innovation and entrepreneurship by bringing young and promising developer talents into their region and play an active part in tackling societal challenges such as climate change or natural disasters with big data from Earth. Benefiting from up to EUR 20,000 from the European Commission, several organisers have held more than one event during the four rounds.

The first images from space were taken on the sub-orbital V-2 rocket flight launched by the U.S. on October 24, 1946

Types of EO (Earth Observations) satellites

Very diverse characteristics, main properties are:

- application domain (meteorology, environmental, agriculture, urban, geosciences),
- sensor types (optical, SAR, other),
- spatial resolution (low, high, very high),
- spectral resolution (number of bands, band width, sensor sensitivity),
- revisit time (hours, days, weeks),
- size (big, small, nano),
- constellation (single, double, swarm),
- ownership (commercial, public).

Satellite Technology

Among the services that satellites can provide for disaster risk management and emergency response are weather forecasting, remote sensing, geo-positioning, navigation, television and telecommunication. Instruments on-board satellites circling the Earth are designed to cover specific wavelength ranges of the electromagnetic spectrum in order to capture images, atmospheric sounding, satellite communication, geo-positioning and navigation.

Kinds of orbits

Satellites are circling Earth in different orbits depending on the type of application or instrument on-board:

- A satellite in a **geostationary orbit** circles the Earth above the equator (0 latitude) synchronously to the Earth's rotation. Its apparently fixed position above a point on the equator at an altitude of more than 36,000km makes it suitable for communications and regional climate observation of that specific area, with high temporal but low spatial resolution.

Kinds of orbits contd.

- Earth observation satellites and satellites for meteorological purposes are located in **low Earth orbit (LEO)** at an altitude of typically about 500-800 km and near polar inclination. Due to their orbit, these satellites provide global coverage with comparatively lower temporal, but medium to very high spatial resolution. Due to the high costs of space transportation, constellations of communication or navigation satellites are also placed in Low Earth Orbit.

Optical and radar sensors

Earth Observation satellites use either optical or radar sensors to capture images of Earth.

Optical sensors for Earth observation are designed to deliver images in either panchromatic spectral format or multispectral format.

Panchromatic refers to images in black and white that are reflected from Earth's surface exposed to all visible light.

Multispectral images usually include four bands of the electromagnetic spectrum: blue, green, red and near-infrared.

Radar sensors for Earth observation are designed to operate in the microwave range.

Data characteristics

There are four types of resolution when discussing satellite imagery:

- **spatial resolution** is defined as the pixel size of an image representing the size of the surface area (i.e. m²) being measured on the ground, determined by the sensors' instantaneous field of view (IFOV);
- **spectral resolution** is defined by the wavelength interval size (discrete segment of the Electromagnetic Spectrum) and number of intervals that the sensor is measuring;
- **temporal resolution** is defined by the amount of time that passes between imagery collection periods for a given surface location;
- **radiometric resolution** is defined as the ability of an imaging system to record many levels of brightness (contrast for example) and to the effective bit-depth of the sensor (number of grayscale levels) and is typically expressed as 8-bit (0255), 11-bit (02047), 12-bit (04095) or 16-bit (065.535);

Data characteristics cont.

- **geometric resolution** refers to the satellite sensor's ability to effectively image a portion of the Earth's surface in a single pixel and is typically expressed in terms of Ground sample distance, or GSD. GSD is a term containing the overall optical and systemic noise sources and is useful for comparing how well one sensor can "see" an object on the ground within a single pixel. For example, the GSD of Landsat is $\approx 30m$, which means the smallest unit that maps to a single pixel within an image is $\approx 30m \times 30m$. The latest commercial satellite (GeoEye 1) has a GSD of 0.41 m. This compares to a 0.3 m resolution obtained by some early military film based Reconnaissance satellite such as Corona.

European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) is an intergovernmental organisation and was founded in 1986. Their purpose is to supply weather and climate-related satellite data, images and products 24 hours a day, 365 days a year to the National Meteorological Services of Member States in Europe, and other users worldwide.

Official site: <https://www.eumetsat.int>

EUMETSATs mission

- To establish, maintain and exploit European operational meteorological satellite systems, while considering the recommendations of WMO as much as possible.
- By fulfilling these objectives, contribute to environmental monitoring, where interactions with the ocean and the atmosphere are involved.
- A further objective is to contribute to operational climate monitoring and detection of global climatic changes.

EUMETSAT has been running a fleet of meteorological satellites, providing weather and climate data, for more than 25 years

NAME	PERIOD	NUMBER
▶ Meteosat First Generation (MFG)	1977–2017	7 geostationary satellites
▶ Meteosat Second Generation (MSG)	2004–2025	4 geostationary satellites
▶ Meteosat Third Generation (MTG)	2021–2039	6 geostationary satellites
▶ Metop	2007–2024	3 polar satellites
▶ EUMETSAT Polar System-Second Generation (EPS-SG)	2021–2040	2 polar satellites
▶ Jason	2009–2036	3 marine satellites
▶ Sentinel-3	2016–2024	2 marine satellites

Current operational Eumetsat satellites

EUMETSAT Programmes Overview

Data service for Marine Environment Monitoring

EUMETSAT Data Centre

Archived data is made available to EUMETSATs users for many different purposes, including meteorological studies and climate research:

- 5 PB of data is currently in the archive,
- 400 GB of data is archived per day,
- about 1,400 orders are processed per month,
- currently, orders averaging 4.2 TB of data per day are executed,
- 20 TB per month are distributed over the Internet,
- in the course of 2014:
 - 299,000 orders have been processed 281,000 of which were standing orders,
 - 8.8 million items were delivered.

Stage of data selection for research

European Organisation for Met... (DE) <https://archive.eumetsat.int/usc/#sf:jd=EO:EUM:DAT:V> 70%

23 35068_8T 10083

Granule Name	Satellite	Instrument	Product Type	Sensing Start Time (UTC)	Sensing Stop Time (UTC)	Product Version	Archive Facility
20190119184500MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 18:45:00	2019-01-19 18:45:00	0	UMARF
20190119170000MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 17:00:00	2019-01-19 17:00:00	0	UMARF
20190119173000MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 17:30:00	2019-01-19 17:30:00	0	UMARF
20190119174500MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 17:45:00	2019-01-19 17:45:00	0	UMARF
20190119180000MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 18:00:00	2019-01-19 18:00:00	0	UMARF
20190119181500MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 18:15:00	2019-01-19 18:15:00	0	UMARF
20190119183000MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 18:30:00	2019-01-19 18:30:00	0	UMARF
20190119184500MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 18:45:00	2019-01-19 18:45:00	0	UMARF
20190119190000MSG4MSGMPEJ00000DPE	MSG4	SEVI	MSGMPEJ	2019-01-19 19:00:00	2019-01-19 19:00:00	0	UMARF

11-20 of 96

SHOW THUMBNAILS REMOVE SELECTED REMOVE UNSELECTED CLOSE

Product Type Multi-Sensor Precipitation Estimate in JPEG - MSG

Orbit Type Geostationary Orbit

Processing Level level 2 MET (No USG C.)

Processing Mode Nominal

Satellite ID Meteosat11(MSG product family)

Archive Facility U-MARF

Instrument ID SEVIRI instrument (MSG)

Spectral Band IDs none

Overall Quality OK

Reception Start Date/Time (UTC) 2019-01-19 17:15:00

Reception Stop Date/Time (UTC) 2019-01-19 17:15:00

Sensing Start Date/Time (UTC) 2019-01-19 17:15:00

Sensing Stop Date/Time (UTC) 2019-01-19 17:15:00

Receiving Centre Primary Ground Station

Product Algorithm Version 0100

Base Algorithm Version 0100

Reference Time (UTC) 2019-01-19 17:15:00

Instrument Mode ALTHRVR

Equator Point Longitude (deg) 0

Disposition Flag Operational mode

Disposition Mode

Processing Start Date/Time (UTC) 2019-01-19 17:20:06

Processing Centre EUMETSAT

Dropped Lines Count 0

Dropped Lines Percentage 0

The stage of ordering data through EUMETSAT portal

The screenshot shows the EUMETSAT User Services Client interface. At the top, the browser address bar displays the URL <https://archive.eumetsat.int/usc/>. The EUMETSAT logo and tagline "MONITORING WEATHER AND CLIMATE FROM SPACE" are visible. The main navigation bar includes "SEARCH AND ORDER" and "USER SERVICES CLIENT".

The "SELECT PRODUCT" section is active, showing a breadcrumb trail: "SELECT PRODUCT > FILTER > DATE/TIME > ROI > FORMAT > DELIVERY METHOD > CHECK OUT". A search term field is present. Under the "Products" tab, a list of datasets is shown, with "Multi-Sensor Precipitation Estimate (JPEG) - MSG - 0 degree" selected. The "Thematic Filter" sidebar on the right lists various categories, with "Precipitation" selected. A "NEXT STEP" button is located at the bottom of the product list.

On the right side, the "Selected Product" section displays the chosen item: "Multi-Sensor Precipitation Estimate (JPEO) - MSG - 0 degree". It includes a satellite image of Earth and a detailed description: "The Multi-Sensor Precipitation Estimate (MPE) product consists of the near-real-time rain rates in mm/hr for each Meteosat image in original pixel resolution. The algorithm is based on the combination of polar-orbiter microwave measurements and images in the Meteosat IR channel by a so-called blending technique. The MPE is most suitable for convective precipitation. Applications and Users' Operational weather forecasting in areas with poor or no radar coverage, especially in Africa and Asia. The polar-orbiter microwave measurement data are crucial for the generation of the MPE product and any unavailability of the data has a direct impact on the availability of the MPE product. The polar-orbiter microwave".

Online, locally, immediately access to Earth observation data, growing by around 26 TB daily

LATEST VOLUME OF DATA PER SATELLITE

LATEST NUMBER OF PRODUCTS PER SATELLITE

Data Offer

BUILDING ON THE LANDSAT LEGACY

<https://discovery.creodias.eu/dataset>

Datasets	Products	Instrument	Locally Held
Sentinel-1A & Sentinel-1B	GRD	SAR C-BAND	Full archive
	OCN		Last 6 months
	RAW		
	SLC		
Sentinel-2A & Sentinel-2B	L1C	MSI	Full archive
	L2A		- Europe: full archive - Last 6 months / orderable
			- Orderable */** - Cached ***
Sentinel-3A & Sentinel-3B	L1 SLSTR	SLSTR	Full archive
	L1 OLCI	OLCI	
	L1 SRAL	SRAL	
	L2 SLSTR (LST/WST)	SLSTR	
	L2 OLCI	OLCI	
	L2 SRAL	SRAL	
Sentinel-5P	L1B	TROPOMI	Full archive
	L2 ****		
Landsat-5	L1G, L1T, L1GT	TM	Coverage of Europe (1984-2011)
Landsat-7	L1G, L1T, L1GT	ET	Coverage of Europe (1999-2017)
Landsat-8	L1T, L1GT	OLI, OLI TIRS	Coverage of Europe
Envisat	L1	MERIS	GLOBAL (2002-2012)
SMOS	L1B, L1C, L2	MIRAS	GLOBAL (2010-present)

High-level layout of the Creodias platform

NASAs Earth Observing System Data and Information System (EOSDIS) has provided various ways to discover, access, and use the data. NASA provides data from many missions:

- Aqua MODIS,
- Terra MODIS,
- SNPP — JPSS-1 VIIRS,
- Envisar MERIS,
- Sentinel-3 OLCI,
- Sentinel-3 SLSTR.

Data available via: <https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov>

NASA's Earth Science Data Systems (ESDS) program oversees the life cycle of NASA's Earth science data from acquisition through processing and distribution. The primary goal of ESDS is to maximize the scientific return from NASA's missions and experiments for research and applied scientists, decision makers, and society at large.

Since 1994, Earth science data have been free and open to all users for any purpose, and since 2015, all data systems software developed through research and technology awards have been made available to the public as Open Source Software (OSS).
Link to ESDS: <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds>

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

U.S. Department of Commerce

NOAA has the following satellites: GOES-S, GOES-16 East/GOES-17 West, Jason-3, Suomi NPP, DSCOVR, NOAA 20, COSMIC-2, which mainly provide information on weather and environmental conditions.

Link to NOAA data collected by the National Environmental Satellite, Data, and Information Service NESDIS:

<https://www.nesdis.noaa.gov/>

National Environmental Satellite Data and Information Service

DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

GISGeography

Free Satellite Imagery From Authoritative Sources by GIS
Geography, last updated: September 28, 2023.

Available at:

<https://gisgeography.com/free-satellite-imagery-data-list>

Ranking of free satellite data made by GISGeography

- 1 USGS Earth Explorer.
- 2 Sentinel Open Access Hub.
- 3 NASA Earthdata Search.
- 4 NOAA Data Access Viewer.
- 5 Maxar Open Data Program.
- 6 Geo-Airbus Defense.
- 7 NASA Worldview.
- 8 NOAA CLASS.
- 9 National Institute for Space Research (INPE).
- 10 Bhuvan Indian Geo-Platform of ISRO.
- 11 JAXAs Global ALOS 3D World.
- 12 VITO Vision.
- 13 NOAA Digital Coast.
- 14 Satellite Land Cover.
- 15 UNAVCO.

Satellites Data Formats

Data collected by instruments from individual satellites are available in many formats. The most common are:

- netCDF,
- native,
- HDF5,
- TIFF,
- JPEG 2000.

A Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagram of the classic netCDF Data Model exhibits its simplicity

The screenshot shows the HDFView 3.0 application window. The title bar reads "HDFView 3.0". The menu bar includes "File", "Window", "Tools", and "Help". The "Recent Files" list shows "C:\User\stori.cooper\AppData\Local\Apps\HDF_Group\HDFView3.0.0\sample\hdf5_test.h5".

The left sidebar displays a tree view of the file structure under "hdf5_test.h5":

- hdf5_test.h5
 - A note
 - Notes
 - arrays
 - 1D String
 - 2D float array
 - 2D int array
 - 2D int8x9
 - 3D int array
 - 4D int
 - ArrayOfStructures
 - Vdata table: PerBlockMeta
 - Vdata with mixed types
 - datatypes
 - images
 - 3D THG
 - Iceberg
 - hst_lagoon_detail.jpg (highlighted)
 - iceberg_palette
 - landcover.umd.199906.jpg
 - pixel interface
 - plane interface

The middle panel, titled "General Object Info", shows details for the selected object:

- Name: hst_lagoon_detail.jpg
- Path: /images/
- Type: HDF5 Scalar Dataset
- Number of Attributes: 5
- Object Ref: 251464

The bottom section of the middle panel, "Dataspace and Datatype", shows:

- No. of Dimensions: 2
- Dimension Size: Image
- Max Dimension: Image
- Data Type: (0.0)

The right panel, titled "Image", displays a preview of the selected satellite image. The image shows a colorful, multi-wavelength view of a lagoon, with various colors representing different spectral bands. A red starburst artifact is visible in the lower right corner of the image.

At the bottom of the window, there is a toolbar with icons for zooming (magnifying glass), panning (four arrows), and other navigation functions. A status bar at the very bottom indicates "No attached palette found, default grey palette used for 3D THG at /images/ [hdf5_test.h5] in C:\User\stori.cooper\AppData\Local\Apps\HDF_Group\HDFView3.0.0\sample\hdf5_test.h5".

Panoply netCDF, HDF and GRIB Data Viewer

Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP)

A common architecture for all Sentinel Toolboxes is being jointly developed by Brockmann Consult, Array Systems Computing and C-S called the Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP). The SNAP architecture is ideal for Earth Observation processing and analysis due the following technological innovations: Extensibility, Portability, Modular Rich Client Platform, Generic EO Data Abstraction, Tiled Memory Management, and a Graph Processing Framework.

Feature Highlights

- Common architecture for all Toolboxes.
- Very fast image display and navigation even of giga-pixel images.
- Graph Processing Framework (GPF): for creating user-defined processing chains.
- Advanced layer management allows adding and manipulation of new overlays such as images of other bands, images from WMS servers or ESRI shapefiles.
- Rich region-of-interest definitions for statistics and various plots.
- Easy bitmask definition and overlay.
- Flexible band arithmetic using arbitrary mathematical expressions.

Feature Highlights cont.

- Accurate reprojection and ortho-rectification to common map projections.
- Geo-coding and rectification using ground control points.
- Automatic SRTM DEM download and tile selection.
- Product library for scanning and cataloguing large archives efficiently.
- Multithreading and Multicore processor support.
- Integrated WorldWind visualisation.

QGIS - The Leading Open Source Desktop GIS

QGIS is a professional GIS application that is built on top of and proud to be itself Free and Open Source Software (FOSS).

Bibliography

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- [11] <https://www.qgis.org>
- [12] <http://step.esa.int/main/toolboxes/snap/>

Precipitation satellite data used in hydrology

Blending satellite and ground precipitation data using geostatistics and ML

The work introduces a geostatistical methodology based on the space–time kriging method that combines satellite and ground precipitation observations exploiting the spatiotemporal interdependence of space–time data for the enhancement of spatiotemporal mapping and analysis, both in terms of spatial resolution and accuracy. The extension of the methodology that incorporates auxiliary information is known as space–time regression or residual kriging (STRK). In this study, the covariates were the post-processed PERSIANN-CCS satellite precipitation data and geographical features.

This study considers annual precipitation data for the hydrological period from 2009/10 to 2017/18. The prediction performance of the proposed method is tested by comparing predictions with the available data for the hydrological year 2016/17, which recorded an average annual precipitation rate close to the historical average.

Digital elevation map of Crete providing the locations of the 53 meteorological stations

Satellite data using for research

PERSIANN Cloud Classification System (PERSIANN-CCS) is a satellite precipitation product developed by the Center for Hydrometeorology and Remote Sensing (CHRS) at the University of California, Irvine (UCI). The PERSIANN-CCS system estimates precipitation basing on categorization of cloud features, derived from satellite images. It uses the variable threshold cloud segmentation algorithm, which provides better clouds separation accuracy in comparison to traditional approach using constant threshold segmentation. Those separated cloud patches are then classified based on their features, which helps assigning the rainfall value for each pixel in each cloud.

For cloud segmentation and classification, long wave infrared (10.2-11.2 μm) measurements from geostationary satellites are processed. To achieve world-wide coverage, images from **GOES**, **GMS** and **METEOSAT** satellites are used. For assigning rainfall estimation values the system uses a neural network trained on vast variety of data sources, like NASA-EOS TRMM and AQUA, NOAA, DSMP and GPM satellites, but also radar cloud reflectivity and rain gauges measurements.

<http://chrdata.eng.uci.edu/>

The screenshot shows the CHRS Data Portal website. The browser address bar displays chrdata.eng.uci.edu. The page header includes the CHRS logo, navigation links (Home, Info, Tutorial, Products, About Us), and the URL <http://chrdata.eng.uci.edu>. A banner image at the top right features a satellite view of Earth with the text "Inspiring research on hydroclimate and water resources".

The main content area is titled "PERSIANN" and includes a sub-header "PERSIANN-CCS PERSIANN-CDR". The text describes the PERSIANN system: "The current operational PERSIANN (Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks) system developed by the Center for Hydrometeorology and Remote Sensing (CHRS) at the University of California, Irvine (UCI) uses neural network function classification/approximation procedures to compute an estimate of rainfall rate at each 0.25° x 0.25° pixel of the infrared brightness temperature image provided by geostationary satellites. An adaptive training feature facilitates updating of the network parameters whenever independent estimates of rainfall are available. The PERSIANN system was based on geostationary infrared imagery and later extended to include the use of both infrared and daytime visible imagery. The PERSIANN algorithm used here is based on the geostationary longwave infrared imagery to generate global rainfall. Rainfall product covers 60°S to 60°N globally. [Further reading.](#)"

Below the text, there are fields for "Data Period: March 2000 - Present", "Coverage: 60°S to 60°N", and "Resolutions: 0.25° x 0.25°".

The right side of the page features a satellite map of the globe. The map is titled "Satelita" and includes a "Map Layers" dropdown menu. The map shows a satellite view of the Earth with a color scale for precipitation. The Google logo is visible in the bottom left corner of the map area.

At the bottom of the page, there are navigation and control elements: "Dataset: PERSIANN", "Time Step: Daily", "Domain: Whole Globe", "Visualization", "Download", "Comparison", and "Subscribe".

Estimates calculated using PERSIANN-CCS system are freecharge available on CHRS Data Portal by Hydrometeorology and Remote Sensing in the University of California, Irvine. The dataset provides global coverage (with exceptions of latitudes above 60° N and below 60° S) with spatial resolution of 0.04° and time resolution of an hour. The data available on the CHRS data portal spans from January 2003 to the present day.

Data Processing Flow

Annual precipitations on the island of Crete through PERSIANN-CCS

Spatiotemporal variogram fit of the theoretical sum-metric model (colored surface)
to the experimental (black line grid)

Spatial distribution of the estimated precipitation using STRK and the sum-metric space time variogram model for the year 2016/17

The major outputs of this work are:

- the successful involvement of a trend model that comprises satellite precipitation data and the spatial distribution of observed precipitation in terms of a specific axis—in this case the easting coordinate direction—in space–time geostatistical analysis of precipitation variations using STRK;
- the successful employment of the joint space–time data interdependence in terms of the sum-metric function which strengthened the efficiency of the spatio-temporal process;
- the improved results compared to previous works in the study area and to similar space–time approaches.

Bibliography

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Satellite data using to analysis of air pollution

Measurements gathered on the surface of Earth provide only the information from the nearest surroundings of the measuring stations, that often cover sparse area. Given the global nature of the problem of air pollution, gathering of data should be practice on the scale of wider areas as to provide further information. Satellite devices that are acquiring such data suffer from certain limitations caused by resolution, number of observations of any given area and inaccuracy or impossibility of measurements caused by a cloud cover. Through comparing the ground and satellite data that have the usage in describing the state of air pollution disadvantages of both of the sources can be overcome. The main problem, however, is a substantial number of data formats, different methods of measuring and various dimensions and scales of the measurement data. This means, that obtaining the valuable information requires acquiring proper datasets, preparing multi-stage data processing and a correct analysis.

Sentinel-5P

The Copernicus Sentinel-5 Precursor mission is the first Copernicus mission dedicated to monitoring our atmosphere. Copernicus Sentinel-5P is the result of close collaboration between ESA, the European Commission, the Netherlands Space Office, industry, data users and scientists. The mission consists of one satellite carrying the **TROPO**spheric **M**onitoring **I**nstrument (TROPOMI) instrument.

- The data are available since May of 2018.
- The data we can download from <https://creodias.eu> or <https://apps.sentinel-hub.com/eo-browser>

Sentinel-5P data products

Details about raw data from Sentinel-5P

- The typical pixel size is $7 \times 7 \text{ km}^2$.
- The data are in NetCDF .nc format.
- Data products from Sentinel-5P's Tropomi instrument are distributed to users at two levels:
 - Level-1B: provides geo-located and radiometrically corrected top of the atmosphere Earth radiances in all spectral bands, as well as solar irradiances.
 - Level-2: provides atmospheric geophysical parameters.

Nitrogen dioxide over Europe - Released 12/03/2019 4:30 pm

Based on measurements gathered by the Copernicus Sentinel-5P mission between April and September 2018, the image shows high levels of nitrogen dioxide in London, Paris, Brussels, western Germany, Milan and Moscow. Nitrogen dioxide pollutes the air mainly as a result of traffic and the combustion of fossil fuel in industrial processes. It has a significant impact on human health, contributing particularly to respiratory problems.

Sulfur dioxide concentration measured by Sentinel-5P satellite

It may be problematic that satellite images are downloaded once a day in the area, and therefore may not be accurate due to the lack of data. Due to the wide measuring field of the satellite, however, it is possible to combine several results in overlapping areas.

<https://browser.creodias.eu>

Another satellite data about air pollution we can obtain from The Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (IASI) from Metop satellite available on Eumetsat. IASI is the main payload instrument for the purpose of supporting numerical weather prediction (NWP). It provides information on the vertical structure of the atmospheric temperature and humidity in an unprecedented accuracy of 1K and a vertical resolution of 1km, which is needed to decisively improve NWP. The use of Metop data in NWP accounts for 40% of the impact of all space based observations in NWP forecasts.

IASI field of view

IASI also measures the fractional cloud cover and cloud top temperature and pressure. The total amount of ozone under cloud-free conditions is measured with a horizontal resolution of 25km and an accuracy of 5%, and total column-integrated content of CO , CH_4 and N_2O with an accuracy of 10% and a horizontal resolution of 100km.

NASA satellites with the MODIS Terra & Aqua instrument

Disciplinary Teams

Web Curator: Brandon Maccherone
NASA Official: Shannell Frazier

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Satellite air quality monitoring with MODIS

← → ↻ 🏠 <https://atmosphere-imager.gsfc.nasa.gov>

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Aerosol Optical Depth

Cloud Optical Thickness

Cloud Effective Particle Radius

Cloud Fraction & Phase

Satellites vs. ground station data

Detection and assessment of pollution

A relationship was found in studies using the Terra satellite belonging to NASA between data on the optical depth of the aerosol (Aerosol Optical Depth - AOD) - the size measured by the satellites instruments - and the dust content suspended PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$ in the air in the United States over space several years, which made it possible to create a complete map of the estimated dust concentration suspended for the whole country, including statistical data from Earth.

Comparison of the average $PM_{2.5}$ results obtained based on satellite data with the results obtained from ground stations between 2001 and 2006 (source [1])

PM2.5 Estimation: Popular Methods

PM_{2.5} estimation based on AOD data from the MODIS instrument [5]

Related works

Analogous studies were also carried out for other sites, including attention to the impact of the conditions prevailing at the observation site on the translation of AOD on dust concentration [2].

Later studies show a relationship between those measured at the earth as the value of another harmful factor - nitrogen dioxide - and observations by satellite using the European satellite operating since October 2017 Sentinel-5P [3, 4].

Due to the short time that has elapsed since launching the satellite too few similar works have been written so far.

Accuracy of measurements due to cloud cover

Important for this type of work is the fact that measurements using satellites are made only during days when there were no clouds over the observed area because the cloudiness preventing data collection. This means limiting the result set to data from the time when weather conditions did not limit the satellite's capabilities. The key to conducting research is determining if satellite data are able give reliable results. So the question should be asked: what is the difference between the pollution observed by satellites and the measured by ground stations when the area studied by the satellite is not obstructed the clouds?

Cloud cover on satellites images

The relevance of this question is due to the lack of satellite results in cloudy days makes it impossible to tell how big the deviation in the results is for areas with particularly frequent cloud cover.

Existing research on this the topic draws attention to the fact that cloudiness introduces results recorded in the long-term (monthly or yearly) time scales relatively low uncertainty even when the presence of clouds in the atmosphere blocks the possibility of collecting measurements in 50% cases [5].

However, it should be remembered that due to physical conditions related to cloud cover, i.e. humidity, as well as limited information on horizontal aerosol decomposition data on dust content in air obtained via satellites, they do not have to translate directly into the content of PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$ [5, 1].

Analysis of satellite data quality based on the model

The main problem with data on air pollution is the fact that satellite instruments measure the number of factors by observing from the exosphere, which is the highest part of the atmosphere. That means data obtained from instruments installed on satellites collect data on the length of the atmosphere, or measures the footprint of the factors studied in the troposphere. appliances spectrometers are usually able to carry out tests at such a large distance and radiometers with a set of models and algorithms that perform predictions on based on photos and measurement data obtained by the satellite.

Problem with common units

The result achieved by orbit research missions are therefore given in the form of particle concentration on surfaces in the atmosphere column. The unit of such measurement is most often molecular mass or number of molecules per surface or Dobson Unit, i.e. unit sometimes used as a description of the overall ozone column in the air, understood as the density (in 10^{-3}cm or 10^{-5}m units) of the layer formed through the ozone column would be reduced to a pressure of 760 Torr (unit of pressure corresponding to 133.3224 Pa) and $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [2]. Ground measurements, on the other hand often measures data in the form of density at the height of land.

CO concentration obtained in Asia for satellite instruments (left) and according to the model (on the right) over two consecutive days [3]

Dependence graph of data obtained from the Pandora measuring instrument concentration in units analogous to measurements of satellite devices and density molecules according to a standard research station, along with regression [4]

Graph showing the concentration of nitrogen dioxide by satellite (red and yellow) and ground stations (blue and purple) when carried out transforming data to a common scale [4]

Direct correlation between satellite and land measurements over the period of one month for Chinese cities [4]

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Part I - Satellite data: acquisition and processing

Part II - Applied satellite data to research

Part III - The use of AI algorithms to analyze satellite data

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The use of AI algorithms to analyze satellite data

Architecture of complete solution

SATELLITE IMAGERY + R

Using 3D residual network for spatio-temporal analysis of remote sensing data

In paper [2], Authors propose an approach to recognize spatio-temporal changes from remote sensing data. Instead of performing independent analysis on each instance of satellite imagery, they proposed a 3D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based on the ResNet architecture. Their approach takes as input a 3D spatio-temporal block comprising of spatial as well as temporal data from multiple years. They predict four key transition classes namely construction, destruction, cultivation and decultivation. In architecture, they introduced Leaky ReLU instead of ReLU which improves the overall performance as it solves the dying ReLU problem. They evaluated their approach in three different cities including Aleppo, Kathmandu and Lahore and showed that proposed model outperformed all the existing 2D convolution based techniques.

Proposed 34 layered 3D ResNet architecture showing introduced Leaky ReLU activations

Residual connection used in all variants as short skip connection. Convolution layer (dotted) is optional to change the dimension of features.

Sample Annotations for four key transition classes. (Row 1) Construction. (Row 2) Destruction. (Row 3) Cultivation and (Row 4) Decultivation.

Table showing quantitative evaluation of the proposed 3D-ResNet-34 architecture and its comparison with state-of-the-art approaches namely Inception-ResNet-v2 and 2D-ResNet-50

Cities	Network Architectures	(Spatio-Temporal Classes) Accuracy					Overall
		Construction	Destruction	Cultivation	Decultivation	No trans. of interest	
Aleppo	Inception-ResNet-v2	16.6%	20%	100%	33%	80%	65.95%
	2D-ResNet-50	25%	25%	100%	100%	69%	58.87%
	3D-ResNet-34	71%	75%	100%	100%	84%	80.14%
Kathmandu	Inception-ResNet-v2	24.5%	25%	100%	100%	77.7 %	57.70%
	2D-ResNet-50	31.9%	33%	100%	100%	70.7%	56.45%
	3D-ResNet-34	48.9%	50%	100%	100%	65%	57.72%
Lahore	Inception-ResNet-v2	44.8%	45%	85.7%	78.3%	57.8%	58%
	2D-ResNet-50	53%	55%	71.4%	74%	51.23%	55%
	3D-ResNet-34	57%	58%	57%	48%	88.4%	75%

3D ResNet representative features shown with its actual image. Out of 128 features, we have visualized only 24 features each of size 8×8 . It can be seen that these features maintain the structural information while encoding the image

Heat map showing construction transition class for Kathmandu city from year 2011 to 2017

2011

2017

Learning and adapting robust features for satellite image segmentation on heterogeneous data sets

Paper [3] addresses the problem of training a deep neural network for satellite image segmentation so that it can be deployed over images whose statistics differ from those used for training.

For example, in postdisaster damage assessment, the tight time constraints make it impractical to train a network from scratch for each image to be segmented.

Authors propose a convolutional encoderdecoder network able to learn visual representations of increasing semantic level as its depth increases, allowing it to generalize over a wider range of satellite images.

Abstract cont.

Authors propose two additional methods to improve the network performance over each specific image to be segmented. As results:

- First, observe that updating the batch normalization layers statistics over the target image improves the network performance without human intervention.
- Second, show that refining a trained network over a few samples of the image boosts the network performance with minimal human intervention.

Authors evaluate their architecture over three data sets of satellite images, showing the state-of-the-art performance in binary segmentation of previously unseen images and competitive performance with respect to more complex techniques in a multiclass segmentation task.

Proposed encoder-decoder convolutional architecture for satellite image segmentation. The architecture of the encoder blocks and units is detailed in the dashed boxes. The architecture of the decoder blocks is detailed in the dotted boxes. "C" stands for the concatenation of feature maps.

Algorithm 1 Training Process

Training NN over training set (source domain)

- 1: **for** $e = 1 \dots n_{train}$ **do** ▷ training over n_{train} epochs
 - 2: $y^s \leftarrow NN(x^s)$ ▷ forward pass
 - 3: $L(w, y^s, t^s) \leftarrow (y^s, t^s)$ ▷ computing loss
 - 4: $J(w, y^s, t^s) = \eta L(w, y^s, t^s) + \lambda R(w)$ ▷ computi. cost
 - 5: $\nabla_w J(w, y^s, t^s) \leftarrow J(w, y^s, t^s)$ ▷ backward pass
 - 6: $v_e = \gamma v_{e-1} + \nabla_w J(w, y^s, t^s)$ ▷ momentum
 - 7: $w_e = w_{e-1} - v_e$ ▷ parameters optimization
-

Algorithm 2 BN Statistics Refinement

Note: NN is first trained according to Alg. 1

- 1: **for** $e = 1 \dots n_{refine}$ **do** ▷ refining over n_{refine} epochs
 - 2: **for** $n = 1 \dots n_{mb}$ **do**
 - 3: $\{u_{n\dots m+n}\} \leftarrow NN(\{x_{n\dots m+n}^t\})$ ▷ forward pass
 - 4: $\mu_{\delta_n} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m u_{n+i}$ ▷ n -th minibatch mean
 - 5: $\sigma_{\delta_n}^2 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (u_{n+i} - \mu_{\delta_n})^2$ ▷ n -th mini-b. var.
 - 6: $z_{\delta_n} \leftarrow \{\mu_{\delta_n} \cup \sigma_{\delta_n}^2\}$ ▷ n -th minibatch statistics
 - 7: $z_n = \alpha z_{n-1} + (1 - \alpha) z_{\delta_n}$ ▷ refining statistics
-

Algorithm 3 Active Learning

Note: NN is first trained according to Alg. 1

Step(a): Selecting representative areas over x_t and extracting patches

$$1: \{x_{1\dots n}^t\} \leftarrow USER(x^t)$$

Step(b): Selecting most uncertain patches

$$2: \{y_{1\dots n}^t\} \leftarrow NN(\{x_{1\dots n}^t\}) \quad \triangleright \text{forward pass}$$

$$3: \{uc_{1\dots n}\} \leftarrow \{y_{1\dots n}^t\} \quad \triangleright \text{computing uncertainty}$$

$$4: \{x_{1\dots n_a}^t\} \leftarrow sort(\{uc_{1\dots n}\}) \quad \triangleright n_a \text{ uncertain patches}$$

Step(c): Labeling n_a patches and refining NN

$$5: \{t^t\} \leftarrow USER(\{x_{1\dots n_a}^t\}) \quad \triangleright \text{labeling patches}$$

$$6: \text{for } e = 1 \dots n_{refine} \text{ do} \quad \triangleright \text{refining over } n_{refine} \text{ epochs}$$

$$7: \quad y^t \leftarrow NN(x^t) \quad \triangleright \text{forward pass}$$

$$8: \quad L(w, y^t, t^t) \leftarrow (y^t, t^t) \quad \triangleright \text{computing loss}$$

$$9: \quad J(w, y^t, t^t) = \eta L(w, y^t, t^t) + \lambda R(w) \quad \triangleright \text{computi. cost}$$

$$10: \quad \nabla_w J(w, y^t, t^t) \leftarrow J(w, y^t, t^t) \quad \triangleright \text{backward pass}$$

$$11: \quad v_e = \gamma v_{e-1} + \nabla_w J(w, y^t, t^t) \quad \triangleright \text{momentum}$$

$$12: \quad w_e = w_{e-1} - v_e \quad \triangleright \text{parameters optimization}$$

Proposed active learning method depicted over three steps. *NN* stands for the proposed neural network, and x^s , t^s , x^t , and t^t denote images and target maps over source and target domains, respectively.

Segmentation performance as IOU and accuracy over INRIA test images (numbers provided by the benchmark organizer)

	IoU [%]					Average	Overall
	Bellingham	Bloomington	Innsbruck	San Francisco	East Tyrol	IoU [%]	Acc. [%]
AMLL [49]	67.14	65.43	72.27	75.72	74.67	72.55	95.91
NUS [49]	70.74	66.06	73.17	73.57	76.06	72.45	95.90
ONERA [49]	68.92	68.12	71.87	71.17	74.75	71.02	95.63
Raisa [49]	68.73	60.83	70.07	70.64	74.76	69.57	95.30
INRIA [48]	56.11	50.40	61.03	61.38	62.51	59.31	93.93
Proposed-18	69.70	66.70	72.16	65.85	73.91	68.50	95.40
Proposed-50	68.17	67.97	73.07	66.78	75.42	69.20	95.52
Proposed-152	69.13	70.30	72.51	69.64	75.31	70.76	95.54
Prop-152 (Norm)	69.47	75.17	75.90	72.76	76.89	73.63	96.10

Results over test area 6 in Bloomington city of INRIA data set. (Left) RGB input image. Score maps (Decoder SoftMax outputs) for the proposed network with 50, 101, and 152 layers follow. As the encoder depth increases, the quality of the score maps improves.

(Left) RGB images from INRIA test set are provided. Each of these images shows an area in the cities of (Top) Bloomington, (Middle) Innsbruck, and (Bottom) San Francisco. (Center) Segmentation maps predicted by the proposed network (152-layer encoder). (Right) Segmentation maps predicted by the adapted network using normalization statistics refinement over each test image.

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Segmentation results over one test area of the Vaihingen test set for the 152-layer encoder network

CDnet: CNN-based cloud detection for remote sensing imagery

In paper [4] Authors utilize the thumbnail (i.e., preview image) of RSI, which contains the information of original multispectral or panchromatic imagery, to extract cloud mask efficiently. Compared with detection cloud mask from original RSI, it is more challenging to detect cloud mask using thumbnails due to the loss of resolution and spectrum information. To tackle this problem, Authors propose a cloud detection neural network (CDnet) with an encoderdecoder structure, a feature pyramid module (FPM), and a boundary refinement (BR) block. The FPM extracts the multiscale contextual information without the loss of resolution and coverage; the BR block refines object boundaries; and the encoderdecoder structure gradually recovers segmentation results with the same size as input image.

Abstract cont.

Experimental results on the ZY-3 satellite thumbnails cloud cover validation data set and two other validation data sets (GF-1 WFV Cloud and Cloud Shadow Cover Validation Data and Landsat-8 Cloud Cover Assessment Validation Data) demonstrate that the proposed method achieves accurate detection accuracy and outperforms several state-of-the-art methods.

Fig. 1. Illustration of cloud–snow coexistence in remote sensing imagery, where cloud and snow regions are sketched by red and blue dotted lines, respectively.

Fig. 2. Discriminative features extracted by CDnet from a ZY-3 satellite thumbnail. (a) Input thumbnail. (b)–(f) Five exemplar feature maps. The cloud, snow, and water regions are sketched by red, yellow, and green dotted lines, respectively.

Framework of the proposed CDnet. Red and green arrows represent the $2\times$ downsampling and $2\times$ upsampling operators, respectively. The red rectangular box with " $\times 2$ " represents the upsampling and BR operations are implemented twice. The operator \oplus represents the element wise summation operator. The first three convolution layers in the modified ResNet-50 use convolutions with stride 2, 1, and 1, respectively, and the filter size is 3×3 .

FPM structure, including multiple parallel dilated convolution layers and a GAP block followed by an upsampling layer

BR block has a residual structure

Cloud detection results for tough cases with cloudsnow coexisting areas. (a) and (b) Two RGB thumbnails. (c) and (d) Two gray thumbnails.

Legend Misclassification

Cloud extraction accuracy [%]

Method	OA	MIoU	Kappa	PA	UA
CDnet(ASPP+GAP)	95.41	89.38	82.05	87.82	89.85
CDnet(FPM)	96.47	91.70	85.06	89.75	90.41

Land-Use Land-Cover classification by Machine Learning classifiers for satellite observations

In [5] article were examined six machine-learning algorithms:

- random forest (RF),
- support vector machine (SVM),
- artificial neural network (ANN),
- fuzzy adaptive resonance theory-supervised predictive mapping (Fuzzy ARTMAP),
- spectral angle mapper (SAM)
- and Mahalanobis distance (MD).

Accuracy assessment was performed by using:

- Kappa coefficient,
- receiver operational curve (RoC),
- index-based validation
- and root mean square error (RMSE).

Results

- Results of Kappa coefficient show that all the classifiers have a similar accuracy level with minor variation, but the RF algorithm has the highest accuracy of 0.89 and the MD algorithm (parametric classifier) has the least accuracy of 0.82.
- The index-based LULC and visual cross-validation show that the RF algorithm (correlations between RF and normalised differentiation water index, normalised differentiation vegetation index and normalised differentiation built-up index are 0.96, 0.99 and 1, respectively, at 0.05 level of significance) has the highest accuracy level in comparison to the other classifiers adopted.

Results cont.

- Findings from the literature also proved that ANN and RF algorithms are the best LULC classifiers, although a non-parametric classifier like SAM (Kappa coefficient 0.84; area under curve (AUC) 0.85) has a better and consistent accuracy level than the other machine-learning algorithms.
- Review concludes that the RF algorithm is the best machine-learning LULC classifier, among the six examined algorithms.

Location map and details of the study area

Description of the land-use/land-cover (LULC) classes identified

Class Name	Class Description	Class Description Example
Agricultural land	Area covered by agricultural crops	
Built up area	Area covered by settlement, road	
Sand bar	Land on the river bed	
Fallow land	Area without vegetation	
Vegetation	Area covered by forest, sparse trees, mango orchard	
River and wetlands	Area covered by water	

Flowchart of the methodology

Optimized parameters for different classifiers used for the LULC modelling

S. No.	Methods	Software Used for Modelling	Optimized Parameters
1	Artificial neural network	TerrSet Geospatial monitoring and modelling system	Hidden layer-1, input layer-1, output layer-1, nodes-6, learning rate-0.01, momentum factor-0.5, sigmoid constant-1
2	Support vector machine	Environment for Visualizing Images (ENVI 5.3)	Kernel type-radial basis function, gamma in kernel function-1, penalty parameter-100, pyramid level-1, pyramid reclassification threshold-0.90
3	Fuzzy ARTMAP	TerrSet Geospatial monitoring and modelling system	F1 layer neurons-12, F2 layer neurons-385, map field layer neurons-6, choice parameter for ART _a -0.01, learning rate and vigilance parameter for ART _a - 1 and 0.98, learning rate and vigilance parameter for ART _b - 1 and 1, iteration 3338
4	Spectral Angle mapper	Environment for Visualizing Images (ENVI 5.3)	Wavelength units-micrometers, Y data multiplier-1, set maximum angle (radian)-single value, maximum angles (radians)-0.100
5	Random Forest	R programming language (R 3.5.3)	-
6	Mahalanobis Distance	Environment for Visualizing Images (ENVI 5.3)	-

a
 Random Forest

b
 Support Vector Machine

c
 Spectral Angle Mapper

d
 Artificial Neural Network

e
 Fuzzy ARTmap

LULC map with different machine-learning techniques

Overall accuracy level of the classifiers

Methods	Kappa Coefficient (K)	Area Under Curve (AUC)	Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
ANN	0.87	0.89	0.09
MD	0.82	0.83	0.28
Fuzzy ARTMAP	0.85	0.86	0.17
SVM	0.86	0.87	0.11
RF	0.89	0.91	0.006
SAM	0.84	0.85	0.23

Validation of LULC of different classifiers with satellite data-derived indices (normalized differential vegetation index (NDVI), normalized differential water index (NDWI), and normalized differential built-up index (NDBI))

Applications of artificial intelligence (AI) for different satellite communication aspects (more details in paper [6])

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